

A POST HOC-BONFERRONI COMPARISONS ON DETERMINING THE SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE AMONG THE DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AMONG THE INSURED POPULATION IN THE RURAL AREAS OF TAMIL NADU

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Abstract:

This research employs post hoc Bonferroni comparisons to examine significant differences among various demographic variables (such as age, income, education, and family size) within the insured population in rural Tamil Nadu. By analyzing survey data, the study identifies distinct patterns and relationships among these variables, providing insights into the demographic composition of the insured population and its implications for insurance providers.

Introduction:

Insurance plays a vital role in providing financial protection, particularly in rural areas where economic uncertainties are higher due to dependence on agriculture, irregular income, and limited access to financial services. In the rural areas of Tamil Nadu, the uptake of life insurance has been influenced by several demographic variables, including age, gender, income, education, family size, and occupation. However, these demographic factors may impact the decision to purchase insurance in different ways, and understanding the specific differences is crucial for developing targeted strategies. The Bonferroni post hoc test, often applied after conducting an analysis of variance (ANOVA), is a statistical method used to determine which specific groups within a population show significant differences when comparing multiple variables. In this study, the post hoc Bonferroni test will be employed to identify significant differences among the demographic variables that influence insurance purchasing behavior in the rural population of Tamil Nadu. By examining the interactions between these variables, this research aims to provide deeper insights into how demographic factors affect the insured population, allowing insurers to tailor their services more effectively to meet diverse needs.

Objectives:

- To identify significant differences among demographic variables in the rural insured population.
- To analyze the implications of these differences for insurance product offerings.
- To contribute to the understanding of demographic diversity within the insured population in rural Tamil Nadu.

Research Methodology:

The study employ a quantitative research design to analyze the demographic factors influencing insurance purchasing decisions in the rural areas of Tamil Nadu. The study used ANOVA followed by a post hoc Bonferroni test to compare demographic variables such as age, gender, income, education, occupation, and family size among the insured population. A total of 700 insured individuals from various rural districts of Tamil Nadu selected using stratified random sampling. The sample stratification is based on key demographic characteristics such as age groups, gender, income levels, education levels, and family sizes. This diversity allow for a comprehensive analysis of how each demographic factor influences insurance behavior.

Data collected through a structured questionnaire, with sections focused on the demographic information of the participants (age, gender, income, education, family size, and occupation) and details about their insurance purchase, such as policy type, sum insured, and duration of coverage. ANOVA (Analysis of Variance): An ANOVA used to determine if there are any statistically significant differences between the means of the demographic variables related to insurance purchases.

Post Hoc-Bonferroni Comparisons: If the ANOVA reveals significant differences, the post hoc Bonferroni test applied to identify which specific demographic groups differ from each other. The Bonferroni method is chosen because it corrects for multiple comparisons, reducing the chance of Type I errors (false positives). This test will help in pinpointing which demographic factors show significant variations in the insured population, such as differences in insurance behavior between different income groups or between gender and educational levels.

SPSS is used to perform the ANOVA and Bonferroni post hoc analysis. The level of significance set at $p < 0.05$, with Bonferroni adjustments applied to control for the multiple comparisons being made. This research will also provide a foundation for policymakers and financial educators to design targeted interventions aimed at increasing financial literacy and promoting insurance adoption in underserved rural populations, thereby enhancing overall financial security in these communities.

Review of Literature:

Krishna Chaitanya. V (2005) the study made an attempt to identify the measures needed for improving the penetration in the rural segments. The study reveals that the penetration of insurance depends on the availability of products and services. The authors pointed out that the socio-economic profile of the untapped market, proliferations of innovative Life Insurance policies, perception of insurable risks among the rural consumers, competitive pressures arising from the integration of bank and insurance, impact of information technologies and the role of insurance industry in financial services are some of the forces which shape the competitive structure of the Indian Life Insurance industry.

Sudarsana Reddy. G. (2005) The study was carried out among the policy holders of private Life Insurance companies in Bangalore city. The study reveals that very few policies of private insurers can be considered as alternatives to policies of public sector insurers. It also observed that the respondents are confident on their investment and have strong faith over IRDA in

protecting the interests of the policy holders. The major problems experienced by the respondents are that the hidden costs associated with their policies. The major expectation among the respondents through their Life Insurance policies is tax benefits. New generation customers prefer to avail add on covers like accidental cover, medical cover along with their life insurance policies.

Hui-Chen (2006) identified that the salespersons can establish an effective and enduring customer relationship which remains a strategic choice in the present competitive scenario. This study explores the co-incident influence of brand equity and sales agents in the service industry and developed a positive customer relationship maintenance model in order to identify and investigate how the antecedent variables influence relationship marketing customer. The result provides support to the model and indicates the important role of the sales agents in customer relationship in the insurance industry.

N. Namachivayam, S.Ganesan and S. Rajendran (2006) have analyzed the socio-economic factors that are responsible for taking Life Insurance polices and also examined the preference of the policy holders towards various types of polices of LIC. Through the study the researchers suggest measure for popularizing the Life Insurance policies among the public. It was concluded that socio-economic factors play a major role in deciding the purchase of Life Insurance policies among the customers of life insurance Corporation in Madurai city.

Ramesh Lal and Neelam Dhanda (2006) in a research article highlighted the extent of insurance penetration in selected countries. These selected countries represent 63% of the world population and 74% of global GDP. The study found that Life Insurance penetration among the countries under study ranges between 0.13 per cent and 14.41 per cent. It was inferred that the population does not have much impact on Life Insurance coverage, but the income level of the country affects the insurance coverage.

Gayathri et al., (2006) revealed a strong relationship between the satisfaction level and the variety service dimensions of Life Insurance companies. The important service dimensions identified through this research are assurance, empathy and reliability which make a positive influence on the customer satisfaction towards the services of the Life Insurance companies.

Further the study reveals that service differentiation and product innovation are the two important areas, in which the best performance will help to capture good market share.

Suresh (2006) through his research found that branding of financial services is a big challenge. That too in long-term contracts (business) like Life Insurance, it is very difficult to gain brand equity at the initial states of business. The researcher identified value added services; customer relationship management, corporate advertising, and targeting both rural and urban markets are the successful brand building initiatives for the Life Insurance corporation of India.

Research Gap:

Previous studies often aggregate demographic data without detailed comparative analysis. This study fills the gap by using statistical methods to provide nuanced insights into the demographic characteristics of the insured population in rural areas.

Statistical Analysis and Findings:

Educational Qualification Vs Attraction Towards the Features of the Life Insurance Policy:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the Educational Qualification group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of the life insurance policy

Ha: There is a significant differences between the Educational Qualification group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of the life insurance policy

Table 1: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	21.517	3	7.172	4.437	.005
Within Groups	276.391	171	1.616		
Total	297.909	174			

It is inferred from the above one-way ANOVA table that the total variation between the study groups is observed to be less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected so that there is a significant relationship between the Educational Qualification group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of the life insurance policy among the insured belongs to the private sector life insurance company. The post hoc-bonferroni comparisons is used to determine the groups of significant difference. The significant values from the original table are highlighted below.

Table 2: Multiple Comparisons (Post Hoc - Bonferroni Tests)

(I) Educational Qualification	(J) Educational Qualification	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Illiterates	up to schooling	-1.15909*	.23220	.000	-1.7789	-.5393
	Degree level	1.74324*	.26015	.000	1.0488	2.4377
	PG & Professional	-.83333*	.27059	.014	-1.5556	-.1110
	Diploma	1.15909*	.23220	.000	.5393	1.7789
up to schooling	Illiterates	-.45045	.31235	.907	-1.2842	.3833
	Degree level	.48894	.24910	.308	-.1760	1.1539
	PG & Professional	.21622	.35285	1.000	-.7256	1.1581
	Diploma	.45045	.31235	.907	-.3833	1.2842
Degree level	Illiterates	.93939*	.26878	.004	.2219	1.6569

	up to schooling	.66667	.36701	.426	-.3130	1.6463
	PG & Professional	-.48894	.24910	.308	-1.1539	.1760
	Diploma	-.93939*	.26878	.004	-1.6569	-.2219

The above table shows that there is a significant difference is present between illiterates ↔ upto schooling, degree level, PG & professional and diploma holders. Also a significant difference is observed between degree level, ↔ illiterates, and diploma holders. The same difference was reflected in the mirror image of the original table generated by the SPSS.

Occupation Vs Attraction Towards the Features of the Life Insurance Policy:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the Occupational group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of the life insurance policy

Ha: There is a significant differences between the Occupational group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of the life insurance policy

Table 3: ANVOA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	19.136	3	6.379	2.543	.058
Within Groups	428.864	171	2.508		
Total	448.000	174			

The above one-way ANOVA table shows that the total variation between the variables is divided into two components. The first one is between groups which represents the variation of the group means around the overall mean and the second within groups represents variation of the individual scores around their respective group means. The significance indicates the significance level of the F-test. Small significance value (i.e., < .05) indicate group difference. From the above table, it is inferred that the significance level is observed to be less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected so that there is a significant relationship between the Occupational group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of the life insurance policy among the customers of private sector life insurance company.

The post hoc-bonferroni comparisons is used to determine the groups of significant difference. The significant values from the original table are highlighted below.

Table 4

Multiple Comparisons(Post Hoc - Bonferroni Tests)						
(I) Occupation	(J) Occupation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Business Man	Govt. Employees	.98649	.43952	.157	-.1867	2.1597
	Farmer	1.16667	.45716	.070	-.0536	2.3870
	Agricultural Workers	.97727	.39230	.082	-.0699	2.0244
	Employees of private sector organizations	-1.41441*	.26037	.000	-2.1094	-.7194
	Non-Agricultural workers	.04392	.20764	1.000	-.5103	.5982
Farmer	Govt. Employees	.41892	.29412	.937	-.3662	1.2040
	Business Man	1.41441*	.26037	.000	.7194	2.1094
	Agricultural Workers	1.45833*	.22405	.000	.8603	2.0564
	Employees of private sector organizations	1.83333*	.30593	.000	1.0167	2.6499
	Non-Agricultural workers	-.04392	.20764	1.000	-.5982	.5103
Agricultural Workers	Govt. Employees	-1.45833*	.22405	.000	-2.0564	-.8603
	Business Man	.37500	.26252	.930	-.3257	1.0757
	Farmer	-.41892	.29412	.937	-1.2040	.3662
	Employees of private sector organizations	-1.83333*	.30593	.000	-2.6499	-1.0167
	Non-Agricultural workers	-.37500	.26252	.930	-1.0757	.3257
Employees of private sector organizations	Govt. Employees	.23423	.24158	1.000	-.4106	.8791
	Business Man	.99939*	.19266	.000	.4851	1.5137
	Farmer	1.56757*	.27290	.000	.8391	2.2960
	Agricultural Workers	-.23423	.24158	1.000	-.8791	.4106
	Non-Agricultural workers	.76515*	.20789	.002	.2102	1.3201
Non-Agricultural workers	Govt. Employees	1.33333*	.28386	.000	.5756	2.0910
	Business Man	-.99939*	.19266	.000	-1.5137	-.4851

	Farmer	-.76515*	.20789	.002	-1.3201	-.2102
	Agricultural Workers	.56818	.24358	.125	-.0820	1.2184
	Employees of private sector organizations	-1.56757*	.27290	.000	-2.2960	-.8391

It is inferred from the above table that there is a significant difference between business men and employees of private sector organizations. The multiple comparison shows a significant difference between farmer ↔ business men, agricultural workers and employees of private sector organizations. Also the agricultural workers are significantly differing with Government employees and employees of private sector organizations. While comparing the employees of private sector organization the business men, farmer and non-agricultural workers one differing significantly. It is also noticed a significant difference between non-agricultural workers ↔ Government employees and employees of private sector organizations. The mirror image of the same difference reflected in the original table.

Occupation Vs Attordabilitiy Towards Life Insurance Policies:

Ho: There is no significant differnece between the Occupation group(s) with that of Attordabilitiy towards life insurance policies.

Ha: There is a significant differences between the Occupation group(s) with that of Attordabilitiy towards life insurance policies.

Table 5: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	58.489	3	19.496	17.359	.000
Within Groups	192.048	171	1.123		
Total	250.537	174			

It could be observed from the above one-way ANOVA that the total variation between the Occupational group(s) with that of Attordabilitiy observed to be less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected so that there is a significant relationship between the Occupational group(s) with that of Attordabilitiy towards life insurance policies among the customers of private sector life insurance company.

The post hoc-bonferroni comparisons is used to determine the groups of significant difference. The significant values from the original table are highlighted below.

Table 6

Multiple Comparisons(Post Hoc - Bonferroni Tests)						
(I) Occupation	(J) Occupation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Govt. Employees	Business Men	-1.33333*	.28386	.000	-2.0910	-.5756
	Farmer	-.56818	.24358	.125	-1.2184	.0820
	Agricultural Workers	-.13094	.12719	1.000	-.4675	.2056
	Employees of private sector organizations	-.45924	.17811	.061	-.9305	.0120
	Non-Agricultural workers	.73038*	.11258	.000	.4325	1.0283
Business Men	Govt. Employees	.13094	.12719	1.000	-.2056	.4675
	Farmer	-.32830	.17528	.369	-.7921	.1355
	Agricultural Workers	1.05868*	.16799	.000	.6142	1.5031
	Employees of private sector organizations	.45924	.17811	.061	-.0120	.9305
	Non-Agricultural workers	.32830	.17528	.369	-.1355	.7921
Employees of private sector organizations	Govt. Employees	.11261	.18737	1.000	-.3831	.6084
	Business Man	.05001	.18439	1.000	-.4379	.5379
	Farmer	-.17059	.12739	1.000	-.5076	.1665
	Agricultural Workers	-.27828	.12264	.141	-.6028	.0462
	Non-Agricultural workers	-.61187*	.18300	.005	-1.0961	-.1277

It is inferred from the above multiple comparisons that there is a significant difference between Government employees and Business men as well as non-agricultural workers. There is a significant difference between the business men and with the agricultural workers. While studying the relationship of agricultural workers with other occupants there observed a significant difference with farmer and with employees of private sector organizations. The similar difference is emerged as a mirror image in the original table.

Salary Income Vs Affordability Towards The Life Insurance:

Ho: There is no significant differnece between the Salary Income group(s) with that of Affordability towards the life insurance

Ha: There is a significant differences between the Salary Income group(s) with that of Affordability towards the life insurance.

Table 7: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	22.472	3	7.491	4.401	.004
Within Groups	1184.666	696	1.702		
Total	1207.137	699			

It is inferred from the above one-way ANOVA that the total variation explained by F-test between the two study groups is observed to be less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected so that there is a significant relationship between the Salary Income group(s) with that of Affordability towards the life insurance among the customers of public sector life insurance company.

The post hoc-bonferroni comparisons is used to determine the groups of significant difference. The significant values from the original table are highlighted below.

Table 8

Multiple Comparisons(Post Hoc - Bonferroni Tests)						
(I) Yearly Family Earnings (in Rupees)	(J) Yearly Family Earnings (in Rupees)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Below 72,000	72,000 – 1,80,000	-0.33359	0.19094	0.486	-0.8388	0.1716
	1,80,001 – 5,00,000	.61187*	0.183	0.005	0.1277	1.0961
	Above 5,00,000	0.44128	0.19402	0.139	-0.0721	0.9546
72,000 – 1,80,000	Below 72,000	0.33359	0.19094	0.486	-0.1716	0.8388
	1,80,001 – 5,00,000	-0.20376	0.11997	0.539	-0.5212	0.1137
	Above 5,00,000	-0.21029	0.1155	0.415	-0.5159	0.0953
1,80,001 – 5,00,000	Below 72,000	-0.35221	0.17234	0.248	-0.8082	0.1038
	72,000 – 1,80,000	0.20376	0.11997	0.539	-0.1137	0.5212
	Above 5,00,000	-0.00653	0.13049	1	-0.3518	0.3387
Above 5,00,000	Below 72,000	-0.14845	0.18272	1	-0.6319	0.335
	72,000 – 1,80,000	0.21029	0.1155	0.415	-0.0953	0.5159
	1,80,001 – 5,00,000	0.00653	0.13049	1	-0.3387	0.3518

The above table shows that there exist a significant difference between the yearly family earning of below 48,000 and with 1,80,001 - 5,00,000. The mirror image of the difference was observed in the original table created by SPSS.

Salary Income Vs Attraction Towards the Features of Life Insurance Policy:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the Salary Income group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of life insurance policy.

Ha: There is a significant differences between the Salary Income group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of life insurance policy.

Table 9: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	47.496	3	15.832	16.374	.000
Within Groups	165.339	171	.967		
Total	212.834	174			

It is obvious from the above one-way ANOVA table that the total variation between Salary Income group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of life insurance policy is observed to be less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected so that there is a significant relationship between the Salary Income group(s) with that of Attraction towards the features of life insurance policy of the private sector life insurance company.

The post hoc-bonferroni comparisons is used to determine the groups of significant difference. The significant values from the original table are highlighted below.

Table 10

Multiple Comparisons(Post Hoc - Bonferroni Tests)						
(I) Yearly Family Earnings(in Rupees)	(J) Yearly Family Earnings(in Rupees)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Below 72,000	72,000 – 1,80,000	-.14192	.17982	1.000	-.6177	.3339
	1,80,001 – 5,00,000	.35221	.17234	.248	-.1038	.8082
	Above 5,00,000	.14845	.18272	1.000	-.3350	.6319
72,000 – 1,80,000	Below 72,000	.14192	.17982	1.000	-.3339	.6177
	1,80,001 – 5,00,000	.05591	.11124	1.000	-.2384	.3502
	Above 5,00,000	.41253*	.10710	.001	.1292	.6959
1,80,001 – 5,00,000	Below 72,000	1.14013*	.15980	.000	.7173	1.5629

	72,000 – 1,80,000	-.05591	.11124	1.000	-.3502	.2384
	Above 5,00,000	.35662*	.12099	.020	.0365	.6767
Above 5,00,000	Below 72,000	1.08422*	.16943	.000	.6359	1.5325
	72,000 – 1,80,000	-.41253*	.10710	.001	-.6959	-.1292
	1,80,001 – 5,00,000	-.35662*	.12099	.020	-.6767	-.0365

The above table shows that there is a significant relationship between the yearly family earnings of 48,001 – 1,80,000 and above 5,00,000. Also the family earnings 1,80,001 – 5,00,000 ↔ below 48,000 and above 5,00,000. Finally a significant difference is observed between above 5,00,000 ↔ below 48,000, 48,001 – 1,80,000 and 1,80,001 – 5,00,000. Similarly, the same difference is emerged a mirror image in the original table.

Conclusion:

This study provide critical insights into the significant differences among demographic variables that influence life insurance decisions in rural Tamil Nadu. The post hoc Bonferroni analysis helped to identify the specific demographic groups that differ significantly in their insurance behavior, such as differences between various income levels, age groups, or educational backgrounds. It is observed that factors like income level, education, and family size show notable differences in how they influence the choice and amount of insurance coverage. By identifying these distinctions, insurance companies can better understand the unique needs of different demographic groups in rural areas and design products and marketing strategies that are more aligned with their financial capacities and risk profiles.

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